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FOREIGN LANGUAGE AS A TOOL OF CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND A MEANS OF WORLD CULTURE LEARNING

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to study the process of involving students of higher educational institutions in world culture, which should be considered as a process of assimilation of universal human values, cultural achievements, traditions, and the foundations of different peoples. The research methodology is the method of theoretical analysis and synthesis, analysis of scientific and methodological literature; comparative analysis, and generalisation of theoretical scientists' views and own pedagogical experience of specialists' training. The scientific novelty consists in determining the meaning of a foreign language not only as an element of artistic and cultural activity but also as the main means of learning about world culture in all its diversity. Taking into account today's situation and conditions of education, the theoretical and practical foundations of the involvement of students in world culture in the process of learning a foreign language are considered, and the approach to the selection of the content of knowledge about the achievements of material and spiritual culture is substantiated. Conclusions. It is noted that nowadays the issue of preservation and development of culture, and spiritual values, created by the peoples over the centuries, appears as one of the most important tasks, as a global issue. The progressive forces of the world cannot but think about the long-term psychological and moral consequences for the youth of violence, aggression, and propaganda. It is claimed that the best form of struggle against spirituality is to oppose it with true spirituality, true culture. Culture is the real basis for dialogue between people and social groups with significantly divergent positions. The use of a foreign language as a way of learning about the world and obtaining special knowledge, assimilation to the culture of different peoples, and dialogue between cultures — are of great importance for higher education. Taking into account the fact that language is a means of cross-cultural communication and knowledge of culture, it can be argued that learning a foreign language serves as a deeper insight into the foundations of world culture.

Keywords: foreign language; world culture; cultural aspect; intercultural communication; higher educational establishments

Introduction

At present, as never before, the question of a closer unification of peoples and states according to various parameters (economic, political, military, geographic) is becoming urgent. In this situation, it is necessary to harmonise the activities of people, their positions, values, and views. Dialogue serves as a means of such harmonisation. Culture is a real basis for dialogue between people and social groups with essentially different positions. In this context, world culture, with its universal values that guarantee the success of dialogue, is of the utmost importance. The use of a foreign language as a way of comprehending the world of special knowledge, exposure to the culture of different peoples, the dialogue of cultures, and the ideas of bilingual education are of particular importance for higher educational institutions in Ukraine.

Recent Research and Publications Analysis. Many sciences deal with the relationship between language and culture, language and society: linguistics, sociology, sociolinguistics, psychology, psycholinguistics, linguodidactics, and ethnolinguistics. The study of language in close connection with the ethnic culture and spiritual life of the people was first addressed by the famous German scientist W. Humboldt (Pajevic, 2016). The problem of the interaction of culture and language is presented in numerous works of scholars (E. Sapir, B. Whorf, C. Lévi-Strauss, H. Steinthal, H. Paul, C. Hagel, D. Hymes, O. Potebnia, and others.) Recently the issues of interaction between language and culture have not ceased to be relevant due to the constant changes in the world and are being studied by domestic and foreign scholars, among them Misić-Ilić Biljana, (2004), Zasićekina, (2014), Myronova, (2018), Kim Deoksoon, (2020), Schmor, Rebecca & Carter, Alanna. (2022). The problem of the relationship between culture and language has been comprehensively discussed, all kinds of studies of the linguistic picture of the world among speakers of a certain language are being carried out, and associative dictionaries of different languages are being created, which provide rich material for studying the peculiarities of perception of reality within a particular culture.

Purpose of the Article

The purpose of the article is to study the process of involving students of higher educational institutions in world culture, which should be considered as a process of assimilation of universal human values, cultural achievements, traditions, and the foundations of different peoples. To examine methods that can be used in teaching a foreign language. Given that the study of a foreign language is likely to serve to deepen understanding of the world culture's basics.

Main Research Material

Given the rapidly changing socio-economic conditions of the information society and current trends in the humanisation and internationalisation of education, the question of introducing a person to world culture is raised promptly. Under familiari-

sation with world culture, we understand the process and result of the knowledge and development of the human values system, the achievements of world culture, the traditions and foundations of different peoples, and the desire for unity and mutual enrichment of national cultures. "Teaching culture is significantly beneficial in terms of language skills, cultural awareness, and changing attitudes towards the behaviors and beliefs of people from another community" (Santos Costa, 2018). The education system is faced with the task of preparing students for cultural, professional, and personal communication with representatives of countries with different social structures, other social traditions, and linguistic and general cultures. As a result, the appeal to the problem of studying a foreign language and culture in the aggregate is becoming increasingly important. "Apart from learning the foreign language, learners should increase their knowledge of the target culture in terms of people's way of life, values, attitudes, beliefs, and how these are manifested in the linguistic categories and forms" (Reid, 2010).

In the 21st century, the language of interpersonal communication is becoming the language of culture — the general culture of the individual, the culture of international cooperation, and the culture of society as a whole. The concept of "culture" is used to characterise the material and spiritual level of development of certain historical eras, socioeconomic formations, specific societies, nationalities, and nations, as well as specific areas of activity or life.

Introduction to the spiritual values reflected in the language and literature being studied means entering a different culture, since the problem of the unity of language and culture, language, and society is considered resolved in science. Language is the guardian of the national culture. "Cultural values are both reflected by and carried through language" (Li, 2013). Therefore, a foreign language should be taught not only as a way of expressing one's thoughts and feelings but also as a source of information about the culture of the people. "Foreign language study expands the linguistic area of experience by affecting language comparisons. It also offers insights into another culture and as such, it is concerned with the human social area of experience" (Touati, 2016). Knowledge of several languages significantly expands the possibilities of a person in the knowledge of culture, the perception of the same phenomenon becomes multidimensional, according to the linguistic and cultural traditions of various societies. "Cultures change; languages change, and the media through which we communicate also change. We are preparing language learners to navigate this innovation, hoping to expand their repertoires so that they can participate appropriately and effectively in new contexts" (Kim, 2020).

The success of the process of familiarising students with the world's cultural values depends on the creation and observance of several pedagogical conditions: subject-activity approach to learning, the communicative and creative orientation of the educational process, inclusion of cultural universals in the content of the educational process; development of incentives and interest in creative knowledge of language and culture; optimisation of the language material in terms of informativeness, compactness, authenticity. Programs based on broad literary, musical, and art history information provide a multidimensional understanding of reality and language as an element of culture.

Solving the problems of mastering the values of world culture in the process of teaching a foreign language is possible only with the complex use of various means that bring students closer to the cultural environment. Through authentic materials that reflect the features of the language, life, and history of the countries of the language being studied, as well as containing comprehensive information about the peoples of the world, the knowledge and development of the world civilisation's values in the process of learning a foreign language is most effective. "Both dynamic and interactive, cross-cultural education emphasises respect, interaction, and understanding between various cultural groups" (Du, 2022).

In the group and collective forms of learning all students are included in the process of dialogic interaction, and the teacher plays the role of an organiser-consultant. The main task facing teachers is to create conditions for the maximum disclosure of the student's creative abilities. The creation of such conditions becomes possible with the intensification of communication between the teacher and students, aimed not only at the readiness of students to participate in all forms of real communication, but also at the development of the ability to various identifications, and as a result, the formation of motivation to understand another culture, the dialogue that promotes mutual enrichment of cultural values, which ultimately ensures the success of students' exposure to world culture in the process of learning a foreign language. Cultural and country study values, typicality, familiarity and relevance to contemporary reality, topicality, and functionality of the phenomena are the most important criteria for selection of the linguo-country study component of the foreign language teaching content. When including a linguo-country study component in the contents of foreign language teaching, adequate means for its assimilation are needed. Such means can be, first of all, authentic materials: literary and musical works, objects of reality, and their illustrative images, which most of all can bring the student closer to the natural cultural environment. Communication of knowledge about the culture, history, realities, and traditions contributes to a positive attitude to a foreign language and the culture of the people of the native speaker.

The selection of linguo-cultural material should be based on the following points:

- Determining the value meaning and value relevance of the selected materials. The materials should help students develop real, unadulterated understandings of the reality, history, and peoples of other cultures, the variability of their lifestyles, and their culturally enriching interactions;
- determination of the extent to which this linguo-cultural material can serve as a stimulus to familiarise students with such key concepts as *cultural heritage*, *cultural community*, *cultural diversity*, *culture of peace*, *multicultural personality*, *dialogue of cultures*, *planetary thinking*, *cultural discrimination*, *cultural aggression*;
- selection of linguo-cultural material from which students could familiarise themselves with ways to protect themselves from cultural aggression and cultural vandalism;
- the appropriateness of using specific selected linguo-cultural material in a particular group of students, taking into account their age and intellectual capabilities.

"Globalisation and new technologies have opened dramatic new opportunities for language teaching and learning" (Thorne, 2003). The use of authentic text, audio,

and video materials reflecting the peculiarities of language, everyday life, life, and history of the countries of the studied language contributes to the effective assimilation of the values of world culture. “With global advancements in multilingual and multicultural education, a consideration of context is essential” (Schmor & Carter, 2022). While discussing topical issues in the educational and pedagogical functions students form language communication skills: the ability to assert attitude and assertiveness, and the ability to take initiative.

“Internet-mediated resources facilitate learners’ acquisition of phonology, grammar, lexicon, and pragmatics, and they provide opportunities to experience aspects of the target culture, as culture is woven into language use” (Kim, 2020). Currently, more and more attention is paid to the development of virtual learning environments for higher education institutions. All new software shells are being developed to become the basis of such tools in various educational institutions. Virtual educational environment plays an important role in non-language universities, or rather one of its components — virtual multimedia learning environment, which can be effectively implemented for intercultural communication. “Using information and computer tools, it is possible to study and understand the cultural values of a foreign language in different ways” (Tynnyi, 2022).

The Internet is of particular relevance nowadays. There are several forms of organising work with the use of info-communication technologies:

– Excursions to websites of www-servers (e.g., galleries of art museums of the world when studying “Art”); inclusion of authentic web materials (text, audio) into the lesson content. All Internet resources can be classified into the following categories:

- electronic versions of mass media (websites of newspapers, television, and radio channels), which are a source of both business and scientific information, covering a wide range of issues of concern to society at the present stage.
- electronic encyclopaedias and reference books (Wikipedia, Britannica), which include information of a general cultural nature;
- official portals of educational and governmental institutions (e.g., websites of world-renowned universities — Oxford, Cambridge, Harvard), which provide the opportunity to review authentic country study material. In the U.S. all the states, ministries, and agencies have their portals, and the White House created the portal Whitehouse.gov.

– Chats are used mainly to get information about the opinions of people from around the world on an issue under discussion in a short period;

– Video, teleconferences, allowing you to present your opinion on a certain topic, to learn the point of view of people from different countries of the world.

The Internet contains a wide variety of resources that can be used in the process of learning a language. By engaging in it during a foreign language class, we create a model of real communication. The various possibilities of working on the Internet not only promote the development of language skills, but also the skills of receiving and processing information, the ability to work with browsers, electronic library systems, reference systems, and databases, and also allow a direct process of communication on various platforms, for example, in Zoom; conduct online conferences,

forums, and using e-mail to send instant mail; make publications, open and design web pages, sites.

The Internet offers a wide range of opportunities in learning English also for students who do not have outstanding language skills. All of them communicate on various sites, and have an opportunity to get acquainted there and with representatives of English-speaking countries.

The desire to connect language and culture in teaching foreign languages has always been relevant and has been repeatedly implemented in the works of scientists. The modern situation in the world requires, and new technologies allow us to pay special attention to the organisation of the learning process. A foreign language allows students to learn the culture and the whole world, and this opportunity should be used.

Conclusions

Culture and language are connected by diverse relationships since they are a single whole. Language is a way of expressing and a means of knowing the culture. Knowledge of a foreign language allows you to reveal the essence of cultural realities more fully and in many aspects and solve the problem of adequate understanding and experiencing the phenomena of culture, both native and foreign. The level of culture that a person acquires in the process of learning a foreign language will be expressed in his competence as a systemic quality of a person, allowing him to realise his individual achievements in terms of mastering a foreign language culture in a specific activity.

Thus, a foreign language allows you to see and comprehend all facets of the culture of the country of the language being studied. Properly organised classes allow students not only to learn a foreign language but also to learn all the subtleties of the culture of the country of the studied language and the world culture as a whole.

References

- Du, N. (2022). Analysis of Teaching Strategies of College English Speculative Reading Based on Big Data Analysis of Student Behavior in Cross-Cultural Education Environment. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 10, 1–11. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363463823_Analysis_of_Teaching_Strategies_of_College_English_Speculative_Reading_Based_on_Big_Data_Analysis_of_Student_Behavior_in_Cross-Cultural_Education_Environment [in English].
- Santos Costa, G. (2018). Language & Cultural in English as a Foreign Language Teaching: A Socio-cultural Experience of Some Exchange Students from Piauí Federal Institute. *Revista Ibero-Americana de Estudos em Educação*, 13(1), 379–390. <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/6198/619866305013/html/> [in English].
- Kim, D. (2020). Learning Language, Learning Culture: Teaching Language to the Whole Student. *ECNU Review of Education*, 3(3), 519–541. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2096531120936693> [in English].
- Li, S. (2013). Culture Teaching in Foreign Language Teaching. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 3(2), 371–375 <http://www.academypublication.com/issues/past/tpls/vol03/02/21.pdf> [in English].

- Misic-Ilic, B. (2004). Language and Cultural Studies - Wonderland through the Linguistic Looking Glass. *Facta Universitatis: Series Linguistics and Literature*, 3(1), 1–15. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357781454_LANGUAGE_AND_CULTURE_STUDIES_-_WONDERLAND_THROUGH_THE_LINGUISTIC_LOOKING_GLASS [in English].
- Myronova, N. (2018). Linguocultural Code: Theoretical Basis of Research. *Problems of Semantics. Pragmatics and Cognitive Linguistics*, 33, 13–15. <https://doi.org/10.17721/2663-6530.2019.35.01> [in English].
- Pajevic, M. (2016). Thinking Language: Wilhelm Von Humboldt Now Introduction. *Forum for Modern Language Studies*, 53(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1093/fmls/cqw079> [in English].
- Schmor, R., & Carter, A. (2022). Pluriculturalism and Plurilingualism in English for Academic Purposes: Challenges and Opportunities. In *Handbook of Research on Teaching in Multicultural and Multilingual Contexts* (pp. 319–336). Global. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363796270_Pluriculturalism_and_Plurilingualism_in_English_for_Academic_Purposes_Challenges_and_Opportunities [in English].
- Thorne, S. (2003). Artifacts and Cultures-of-Use in Intercultural Communication. *Language Learning and Technology*, 7(2), 38–67. <https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/45aa3488-0ec8-49d5-b58a-6eb82257f8db/content> [in English].
- Touati, M. (2016). *The Integration of Culture in Foreign Language Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.35813/1712-000-006-015> [in English].
- Tynny, V. (2022). Enhancing Intercultural Communication During Foreign Language Learning via Digital Technologies. *Grail of Science*, 4, 415–418. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351679082_ENHANCING_INTERCULTURAL_COMMUNICATION_DURING_FOREIGN_LANGUAGE_LEARNING_VIA_DIGITAL_TECHNOLOGIES [in English].
- Reid, E. (2010). Culture — an inevitable part of a foreign language teaching. In *Modernisation of Teaching Foreign Languages: CLIL, inclusive and intercultural education* (pp. 199–215). Brno. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262673666_Culture_-_an_inevitable_part_of_a_foreign_language_teaching [in English].
- Zasiekina, L. (2014). Culture Effects on Language and Cognition in Psycholinguistic Experiment. *East European Journal of Psycholinguistics*, 1, 235–242. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/301359153_CULTURE_EFFECTS_ON_LANGUAGE_AND_COGNITION_IN_PSYCHOLINGUISTIC_EXPERIMENT [in English].

ІНОЗЕМНА МОВА ЯК ІНСТРУМЕНТ МІЖКУЛЬТУРНОГО СПІЛКУВАННЯ ТА ЗАСІБ ПІЗНАННЯ СВІТОВОЇ КУЛЬТУРИ

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Анотація

Мета статті — дослідити особливості залучення студентів закладів вищої освіти до світової культури, яке слід розглядати як процес засвоєння загальнолюдських цінностей, культурних здобутків, традицій та засад різних народів. Методологія дослідження спирається на метод теоретичного аналізу та синтезу, аналіз науково-методичної літератури, порівняльний аналіз, узагальнення теоретичних поглядів науковців та власного педагогічного досвіду підготовки фахівців. Наукова новизна полягає у визначенні значущості іноземної мови не лише як елемента художньо-культурної діяльності, а і як основного засобу пізнання світової культури у всьому її розмаїтті. Враховуючи обставини та умови освіти, розглянуто теоретичні та практичні основи залучення студентів до світової культури у процесі вивчення іноземної мови, обґрунтовано підхід до відбору змісту знань про досягнення матеріальної та духовної культури, культурні здобутки, традиції та звичаї різних народів. Висновки. Зазначено, що нині проблема збереження та розвитку культури, духовних цінностей, створених народами протягом століть, постає як одне з найважливіших завдань, як глобальна проблема. Прогресивні сили світу не можуть не думати про довгострокові психологічні та моральні наслідки для молоді насильства, низинних інстинктів людини, пропаганди. Зауважено, що найкраща форма боротьби з бездуховністю — це протиставлення їй справжньої духовності, культури. Культура є реальною основою для діалогу між людьми та соціальними групами з суттєво розбіжними позиціями. Значущим для закладів вищої освіти є використання іноземної мови як способу пізнання світу та отримання спеціальних знань, прилучення до культури різних народів, діалогу культур. Зважаючи на те, що мова є засобом міжкультурного спілкування та пізнання культури, можна стверджувати, що вивчення іноземної мови слугує поглибленому проникненню в основи світової культури.

Ключові слова: іноземна мова; світова культура; культурологічний аспект; міжкультурна комунікація; заклади вищої освіти

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